

Semi-empirical Calculation of Activation Energy for a Number of Bimolecular Reactions Part III.

M. B. PAHARI and RAMA BASU

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

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The modified magic formula is used for the calculation of activation energies of halogen-hydrogen halide reactions and to reactions of alkalis, nitrogen and oxygen. The calculated values of activation energies are compared with some other theoretical data where available.

IN recent communications^{1,2} a new method for the calculation of activation energies using modified magic formula has been applied successfully to a number of bimolecular reactions including the addition reactions of ethylene where the systems have no non-bonding electrons. It has been shown that the calculated activation energies are in good agreement with the experimental data where available and those calculated by Noyes³ and Benson and Haugen⁴.

The object of the present investigation was to extend the modified magic formula¹ to the calculation of activation energies of some more bimolecular reactions

In this paper the activation energies of some Halogen-Hydrogen Halide reactions and the activation energies of reactions involving alkalis, nitrogen and oxygen are calculated by the method of "Modified Magic Formula"¹.

The method of calculating the activation energies is discussed below.

Method of Calculation

The "Magic Formula" as proposed by Mulliken¹⁰ for molecules in their ground states is

$$E = \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}} A_i I_{ij} \frac{S_{ij}}{1+S_{ij}} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k,l \\ k \neq l}} \nu A_k I_{kl} S_{kl}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{m,n \\ m \neq n}} K_{mn} - P + RE \quad \dots (1)$$

where A_i , A_k and ν are constants, S_{ij} and S_{kl} are overlap integrals for bonded attraction and non-bonded repulsion respectively, I_{ij} and I_{kl} refer to mean ionization energies for the two orbitals involved, K_{mn} is the non-bonded attraction term involving $\sigma-\pi$ pairs, P and RE are known as promotional energy and resonance energy respectively,

The constants have the following values as suggested by Mulliken

$$\nu = 0.7$$

$$A_i \text{ \& } A_k = 1.16 \text{ for } \sigma\text{-bonds} \\ = 1.53 \text{ for } \pi\text{-bonds}$$

Neglecting those terms which are not functions of overlap integrals and writing the non-bonded overlap integrals in terms of the bonded overlap integrals we write the "modified magic formula"¹¹ as

$$E(r) = \sum_{i \neq j} A_i I_{ij} \frac{S_{ij}(r)}{1+S_{ij}(r)} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k \neq l} \nu A_k I_{kl} X^2 S_{kl}^2(r) \quad \dots (2)$$

where X is a suitable multiple to be determined.

For diatomic molecules the equation (2) reduces to

$$E(r) = A_i I_{ij} \frac{S_{ij}(r)}{1+S_{ij}(r)} - \frac{1}{2} \nu A_k < I > X^2 S_{ij}^2(r) \quad \dots (3)$$

where $< I >$ has been taken as the average Ionization potential for various non-bonded states.

In simple form the equation (3) can be put as

$$D = a_1 \frac{S}{1+S} - a_2 X^2 S^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where,

$$S_{ij}(r) = S$$

$$a_1 = A_i I_{ij}$$

$$a_2 = (\nu/2) A_k < I >$$

Since the quantities a_1 and a_2 are constants for known values of ν , A_i , A_k , I_{ij} and I_{kl} the 'modified magic formula' for a diatomic molecule can be established if X^2 is known for that diatomic molecule.

To calculate X^2 equation (5) is set up from the equation (4) corresponding to the bond dissociation energy, D_e , and the equilibrium internuclear distance r_e .

$$D_e = a_1 \frac{\bar{S}}{1+\bar{S}} - a_2 X^2 \bar{S}^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

where $S_{ij}(r = r_e) = \bar{S}$.

Equation (5) with the help of the condition

$$\left(\frac{\delta D}{\delta \bar{S}}\right)_{r=r_e} = 0$$

[Justification is given in the previous communication¹] gives X^2 and S for a particular diatomic molecule when the corresponding a_1 , a_2 and the bond dissociation energy D_e are known.

Parameters needed to establish the "Modified Magic Formulae" for several diatomic molecules are given in an earlier communication¹. Some more parameters are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1—IONIZATION POTENTIAL OF ELEMENTS (IN E.V.)⁶.

Elements	Ionization potential (e.v.)
N	14.54
Na	5.14
O	13.60

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS USED TO SET UP "MODIFIED MAGIC FORMULAE"

Molecules	Dissociation energies (D_e) K Cal/mole	Equilibrium internuclear separations (r_e) Å	The Calculated values of \bar{S}	X^2 values to set up modified magic formulae
Na ₂	17.53	3.078	0.2669	3.3348
NaH	48.68	1.887	0.4273	1.6412
NaCl	98.54	2.361	1.1314	0.2779
NaI	71.41	2.712	0.8646	0.4752
NaBr	88.45	2.502	0.9065	0.4335
N ₂	228.37	1.094	2.2643	0.0592
O ₂	120.22	1.207	0.8334	0.5099
NO	152.72	1.151	1.1298	0.2787
OH	106.84	0.971	0.7107	0.6868

The "modified magic formulae" as established for different diatomic molecules are given in Table 3.

Extension of the Modified Magic Formulae to the activated complex :

The bond energy E of the activated complex is written as

$$E = \sum_{i=1,3} K_i \frac{S_i}{1+S_i} b - \sum_{i=1,3} K'_i S_i^2 + \sum_{j=2,4} K_j \frac{S_j}{1+S_j} (1-b) - \sum_{j=2,4} K'_j S_j^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

TABLE 3—MODIFIED MAGIC FORMULAE FOR DIFFERENT DIATOMIC MOLECULES

Molecules	Modified magic formulae *	
	Attractive term	Repulsive term
H ₂	$D = 15.7528 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 3.5572 S^2
F ₂	$D = 21.5760 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 53.2599 S^2
Cl ₂	$D = 15.0916 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 11.4515 S^2
Br ₂	$D = 15.9152 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 19.1129 S^2
I ₂	$D = 12.2960 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 14.5255 S^2
HF	$D = 18.6644 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 3.4792 S^2
HCl	$D = 15.4222 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 3.5431 S^2
HBr	$D = 15.8340 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 5.6361 S^2
HI	$D = 14.0244 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 5.9030 S^2
ClF	$D = 18.3280 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 17.3148 S^2
BrF	$D = 18.7456 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 21.3625 S^2
IF	$D = 16.9360 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 21.6903 S^2
BrCl	$D = 15.5034 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 14.3859 S^2
ICl	$D = 13.6880 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 11.2143 S^2
IBr	$D = 14.1056 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 12.9427 S^2
Na ₂	$D = 5.9624 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 6.9591 S^2
NaH	$D = 10.8576 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 6.2369 S^2
NaCl	$D = 10.5212 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 1.0233 S^2
NaI	$D = 9.1292 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 1.5183 S^2
NaBr	$D = 10.9388 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 1.6597 S^2
N ₂	$D = 16.8664 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 0.3495 S^2
O ₂	$D = 15.7760 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 2.8155 S^2
NO	$D = 16.3212 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 1.5920 S^2
OH	$D = 15.7644 \frac{S}{1+\bar{S}}$	— 3.7894 S^2

where b is a measure of the extent to which the parent bonds has been broken during the reaction and

$$K_i = K_j = A_i \cdot I_{ij}$$

$$K'_i = K'_j = \frac{\nu}{2} A_k < I > X^2$$

are known constants.

The condition of the transition state theory

$$\frac{\delta E}{\delta S_i} = 0$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ gives four cubic equations involving the bond order b and the overlap integrals S_1, S_2, S_3 & S_4 .

For different values of b the above cubic equations give different values of S_1, S_2, S_3 & S_4 which in turn give different values of E from the equation (6). Plotting b against E we get the minimum energy E for the activated complex. The activation energy is the difference between the minimum energy E of the activated complex and the sum of the ground state energies of the parent molecules.

Results and Discussion

The activation energies of the following reactions are calculated by the method discussed above. Reactions are grouped by chemical similarity in the following tables (Tables 4 and 5) and are designated by reactant molecules. The extent of reaction α^\ddagger as calculated by Noyes³ are compared with our b values in the last column of the tables 4 and 5. Independent estimation of activation energies of bimolecular reactions by Noyes³ and by Benson-Haugen⁴

are reported as E_N and E_{BH} in two columns of tables (4 and 5). The calculated activation energies (E_{calc}) by the present method are reported in a separate column.

Fig. I-1. Plot of E (the energy of the activated complex) versus b (the reaction coordinate). Reactions involving Alkalies, Nitrogen and Oxygen.

In Table 4, the activation energies of reactions involving alkalies, nitrogen and oxygen are calculated. The experimental activation energies^{6,7,8} are compared with E_{calc} . It is found that best agreement is obtained for the reaction $2\text{NaH} = \text{Na}_2 + \text{H}_2$. The other values of E_{calc} are nearly same as those of E_N . No E_{BH} data is available. In this connection it is to be pointed out that the experimental

TABLE 4—KINETICS OF REACTIONS INVOLVING ALKALIES, NITROGEN AND OXYGEN

Sr. No.	Reactants	Expt. activation energy (6,7,8) K cal/mole	E_N K cal/mole	E_{BH} K cal/mole	E_{calc} K cal/mole	Comparison of α^\ddagger values of Noyes with b values	
1.	2NO	63.1	54.0	—	43.56	0.6125	0.4240
2.	H ₂ +O ₂	39.0	77.9	—	68.17	0.4800	0.5360
3.	Na ₂ +Cl ₂	—	1.1	—	2.3	0.8000	0.0880
4.	2NaH	24.9	27.1	—	24.89	0.6250	0.4160
5.	Na ₂ +HCl	—	33.1	—	27.66	0.5900	0.4400
6.	NaH+Cl ₂	—	9.3	—	12.38	0.8050	0.2210
7.	NaH+HCl	—	38.5	—	26.54	0.6700	0.3990

TABLE 5—KINETICS OF HALOGEN-HYDROGEN HALIDES REACTIONS

Sr. No.	Reactants	Expt. activation energies K cal/mole	E_N K cal/mole	E_{BH} K cal/mole	E_{calc} K cal/mole	Comparison of α^\ddagger values of Noyes with b values	
1.	HI+Br ₂	—	21.5	42.0	34.89	0.445	0.565
2.	HI+IBr	—	21.8	35.4	39.33	0.459	0.525
3.	HI+Cl ₂	—	21.9	46.7	34.17	0.416	0.600
4.	HI+ICl	—	22.3	36.5	33.88	0.439	0.565
5.	HI+F ₂	—	9.1	—	18.88	0.254	0.735
6.	HI+IF	—	14.1	—	23.05	0.328	0.675

activation energies of the reactions $2\text{NO} = \text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$ and $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 = 2\text{OH}$ are in strong disagreement with the values of E_N and E_{calc} . The reaction $\text{Na}_2 + \text{Cl}_2 = 2\text{NaCl}$ is a fast reaction. The E_{calc} value is very small. No experimental data has been reported as yet. The value of b for the above reactions are very high. This has also been observed in the reactions involving fluorine atoms¹.

Fig. I-2. Plot of E (the energy of the activated complex) versus b (the reaction coordinate). Reactions involving Alkalies, Nitrogen and Oxygen.

Fig. I-3. Plot of E (the energy of the activated complex) versus b (the reaction coordinate). Reactions involving Alkalies, Nitrogen and Oxygen.

Table 5 compares the activation energies of some halogen and hydrogen halide reactions as calculated by Noyes, Benson-Haugen and our present method. The E_{calc} are in better agreement with the values of E_{BH} than with the values of E_N . If the proposed model is true, the calculated values of E_N need further verifications.

The energy diagrams of the activation process are shown in Figures I-1, I-2, I-3 and I-4.

Fig. I-4. Plot of E (the energy of the activated complex) versus b (the reaction coordinate). Halogen-Hydrogen Halide reactions.

Conclusion

The construction of potential energy surfaces by contour energy diagrams due to Eyring and Polanyi⁹ is a laborious process and needs much time and energy. The present simple mathematical formulation is indeed satisfactory to get an understanding about the quantitative measures of the activation energies. This method does not calculate the activation energy as the difference in two large total energy terms. It calculates directly an energy difference between reactants and the activated complex. The time required to study one simple reaction with a desk calculator was about one man-day.

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